

THE “N” FRAMEWORK – A POTENTIAL SOLUTION TO NUMERACY ACROSS THE CURRICULUM

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Numeracy is often referred to as an essential skill that all people should possess in order to engage fully in society. Governments and policymakers around the world are encouraging teachers to teach numeracy across the curriculum. This paper proposes a theoretical framework of teacher knowledge for the integration of numeracy across the curriculum in post-primary schools in Ireland. Teacher knowledge is complex and consists of many different facets of knowledge. The proposed framework integrates theories from existing models of general teacher knowledge (Shulman, 1986), with models of subject specific teacher knowledge (Ball, Thames and Phelps, 2008), and with a numeracy model developed by Goos, Geiger and Forgasz (2014). This enabled the authors to develop an integrated framework of numeracy knowledge and skills, subject-specific knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge which are all essential components of knowledge for teaching in the 21st century. Teachers need to have a deep understanding of these different types of knowledge to teach students effectively in any subject across all subjects.

INTRODUCTION

Being numerate is an essential part of daily life and it involves much more than being able to complete basic mathematical operations (Goos, Geiger, Dole, Forgasz, & Bennison, 2019). Governments and policymakers have noted that numeracy, referred to as mathematical literacy in some countries, is a lifelong skill which needs to be addressed. However, the term numeracy often carries different meanings. Internationally, the concept of numeracy/mathematical literacy is defined by OECD Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) (2016, p.5) as:

...an individual’s capacity to formulate, employ, and interpret mathematics in a variety of contexts. It includes reasoning mathematically and using mathematical concepts, procedures, facts and tools to describe, explain and predict phenomena. It assists individuals to recognise the role that mathematics plays in the world and to make the well-founded judgments and decisions needed by constructive, engaged and reflective citizens.

Frejd and Geiger (2018) discovered that mathematical literacy had different meanings in different countries. While there is not a broadly-accepted definition of numeracy/mathematical literacy, the focus of developing people’s mathematical literacy is to “use mathematics to participate effectively in society and to contribute in a productive and critical manner” (Frejd & Geiger, 2018, p.3). In order to improve and develop students’ levels of numeracy, teachers’ knowledge of numeracy must first be addressed and their knowledge of how to embed numeracy across the curriculum also needs to be considered.

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE TEACHING OF NUMERACY ACROSS CURRICULUM

Ireland's poor performance in PISA 2009 and the decline in students' mathematical literacy led to the implementation of new teaching strategies to ensure that the young people of Ireland are numerate by the time they complete compulsory schooling. The introduction of *The National Strategy to Improve Literacy and Numeracy among Children and Young People 2011-2020* (DES, 2011) was presented as a response to improve students' literacy and numeracy levels in Ireland. The strategy states that all teachers should embed numeracy in their lessons to improve the numerate abilities of the students. To implement this teaching strategy effectively, teachers must be aware of the various approaches, methodologies and interventions that they can use to teach numeracy across all areas of the curriculum (DES, 2011). Teachers need to be able to help students understand the use and application of numeracy across a variety of subjects if this goal is to be achieved.

Researchers in Australia have shown, that in order for teachers to improve the numerate abilities of their students, teachers must first equip themselves with the necessary skills to develop their own understanding of how mathematical concepts and numeracy affect their own lives and their subject area (Leder, Forgasz, Kalkhoven, & Geiger 2015; Goos, Geiger, & Dole 2013). Bennison (2015) acknowledges that within every subject, teachers can exploit numeracy learning opportunities; however, the teacher first needs to identify numeracy opportunities within their specific subject area. Westwood (2008) found that teachers play a key role in enhancing the teaching and learning of numeracy throughout the students' school experience, which in turn will help young people to appreciate and enjoy the mathematics they encounter throughout their lives. The Literacy and Numeracy Strategy, implemented in schools and communities across Ireland, emphasised that the teaching and learning of numeracy skills is not only the responsibility of the mathematics teacher but instead should be a priority across all post-primary subjects (DES, 2011). For teachers to identify numeracy opportunities of learning within their subject area, they must first understand the concept of numeracy and possess a knowledge of numeracy along with other components of knowledge required for teaching.

IMPORTANCE OF TEACHER KNOWLEDGE

Teacher knowledge can be described in many ways. In general, it is the knowledge that teachers possess and how they convey their knowledge to their students. It is evident from the literature on teacher education that teacher knowledge is essential for effective teaching. Hence, in order for teachers to teach effectively in the 21st Century, it is crucial that they develop high levels of proficiency in the areas of Numeracy Knowledge and Skills, Subject Specific Knowledge and Pedagogical Content Knowledge.

Fennema and Franke (1992) use the example of the mathematics teacher needing mathematical knowledge to enable them to teach their students effectively. Using this example, the same can be said for numeracy knowledge and skills, in that a teacher needs to have the knowledge and understanding of numeracy in order to develop their students' numerate abilities in their specific subject area. Teachers need to possess a good knowledge

of numeracy and be able to identify numeracy opportunities within their subject area in order to teach it effectively. In order to create a teacher knowledge framework for numeracy across the curriculum, an in-depth analysis of frameworks of teacher knowledge was conducted. Many researchers have sought to identify what knowledge a teacher should possess in order to teach effectively in the classroom (Shulman 1986; Fennema & Franke 1992; Van Driel, Verloop, & De Vos 1998; Mishra & Koehler 2006; Rowland 2007; Ball et al 2008). It was found that many researchers have different beliefs on what makes a good model of teacher knowledge, with some academics believing some aspects of knowledge to be more important than others.

It was concluded that the frameworks proposed by Shulman (1986) and Ball et al. (2008) were the most suitable to use as the foundation of the new framework for teaching numeracy across the curriculum. It is important to include Shulman's (1986) theoretical framework as it is not specific to teaching one subject, whereas all other frameworks analysed were specific to mathematics, science or technology teaching. Ball et al. (2008) further refined Shulman's categories of teacher knowledge by dividing the subject matter knowledge proposed by Shulman into common and specialised content knowledge. This is very important for teaching as it identifies the different types of knowledge a person such as an economist or scientist should have, while also encompassing the knowledge a teacher of economics or science should possess specifically for teaching. Ball et al. (2008) also created a separate section for pedagogical content knowledge which included curricular knowledge as put forward by Shulman (1986). The models of teacher knowledge for the "N" framework are discussed below in detail.

Models of Teacher Knowledge

Shulman (1986) emphasises the need for teachers to develop three categories of knowledge in their teaching; subject matter knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and curricular knowledge.

Subject matter knowledge is "the amount and organization of knowledge per se in the mind of the teacher" (Shulman, 1986, p.9). Subject matter knowledge is the cornerstone upon which all other domains are developed. Shulman (1986) suggested that the teacher must not only understand the subject matter themselves but also be in a position to explain the content in a way that the student understands. Pedagogical content knowledge is the knowledge required to convey the subject matter knowledge to students through the practice of teaching. Shulman (1986) highlights that pedagogical content knowledge represents the "blending of content and pedagogy into an understanding of how particular topics, or issues are organised, represented and adapted to the diverse interests and abilities of learners" (Shulman 1987, p.8). Shulman (1987) also recognises that pedagogical content knowledge is the domain which will differentiate a person who is a specialist in a particular subject area from a teacher in that subject area. Furthermore, Shulman (1986) discusses curricular knowledge, which is the knowledge required to teach the subject matter and relate it to other topics in other subject areas. By doing this, it gives the student a better learning experience and also reiterates the fact that many topics and subjects are interrelated.

Ball et al. (2008) developed a model of teacher knowledge based on the theories put forward by Shulman (1986) but specific to teaching mathematics at primary level. Subject matter knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge were underlying features of this model. Ball et al. (2008) further defined subject matter knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge by developing different subcategories within each domain. The subcategories for subject matter knowledge were common content knowledge, specialised content knowledge and knowledge at the mathematical horizon. Ball et al. (2008) explain common content knowledge as the knowledge that teachers should have in order to solve problems mathematically, using their mathematical knowledge. Following on from common content knowledge, Ball et al. (2008) discuss knowledge at the mathematical horizon, which is an awareness of how mathematical concepts taught in early childhood will have an effect on students' understanding in later years and how this knowledge is crucial in the teaching of mathematics. Ball et al. (2008) explain that while specific mathematical concepts may not be relevant to the student now, the teacher must remember that they are preparing the students for mathematical topics they will encounter in the future. Ball et al. (2008) describe the scenario where teachers need knowledge beyond what they are teaching. This is described as specialised content knowledge and is a very important domain in any model of teacher knowledge. It is the difference between a scientist or a mathematician teaching the content and a science or mathematics teacher teaching the content. A teacher needs to be able to explain the reasoning behind a procedure, whereas it is sufficient for a scientist to only know how to carry out the procedure; he/she does not need to know the reason why they are carrying out such procedures. Ball et al. (2008) describe this domain as a unique domain; it is the type of knowledge that is not needed for anything else other than teaching.

Ball et al. (2008) then focus on pedagogical content knowledge, which is again split into three aspects: knowledge of content and students, knowledge of content and teaching and knowledge of content and curriculum. When teachers are competent in the domain of knowledge of content and students, they are able to predict/anticipate students' answers and misconceptions. Ball et al. (2008) describe this domain as knowing the students and knowing the mathematics being taught. The next aspect in the pedagogical domain, knowledge of content and teaching, is described by Ball et al. (2008, p. 401) as "knowing about teaching and knowing about mathematics". This is the knowledge teachers use to determine how to sequence the topics they teach from the syllabus. The reason teachers need to have knowledge of content and teaching is because the teacher knows that the students must understand a certain topic before moving onto a more complex area in the subject. This decision making by the teacher requires the teacher to have a knowledge of the subject (in which case Ball et al. (2008) use mathematics as the subject) and a knowledge of pedagogy which they believe will affect the students' learning. Finally Ball et al. (2008) emphasise the need for knowledge of content and curriculum which has been discussed in detail by many other researchers in the field and was first introduced by Shulman (1986). Again Ball et al. (2008) highlight the need for teachers to gain the knowledge of the content and the curriculum, requiring the teacher to understand fully what resources they will use and how they will utilise the resources to enable an optimal learning experience for their students without straying too far from the curriculum.

Model of Numeracy

While the models of teacher knowledge discussed above are important, numeracy knowledge did not appear in any of the models of teacher knowledge. Numeracy is a new concept and not easily defined (Jablonka 2015; Goos et al. 2019). There are many different interpretations of numeracy from basic mathematics to a much broader definition put forward by Goos et al. (2014) when they developed a model for Numeracy in the 21st century. For the purpose of this research, we analysed many different definitions of numeracy (Crowther 1959; Cockcroft 1982; Goos et al. 2014; Organisation of Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD] 2016) and found Goos et al. (2014) to be the most appropriate for this study as it was developed specifically to support teachers in embedding numeracy across the curriculum. The model based on the multidimensional nature of numeracy. Goos et al. (2014) firstly describe the different *contexts* in which people will encounter the need to use numeracy i.e. personal and social lives, in work and employment. The next element described in the model is *mathematical knowledge*. This encompasses all the mathematical skills, knowledge and problem solving strategies one will require (in terms of both knowledge and application) to participate fully in society and the workplace. *Dispositions* are the next element defined as an essential part of model. A person's confidence and willingness to use mathematical skills to engage fully in society is a vital component of being numerate. To be able to use different materials and digital *tools* to help gain an understanding of numeracy was another element. All of the elements *contexts*, *mathematical knowledge*, *dispositions* and *tools*, are rooted in a *critical orientation*, which is the ability to use all of the skills and knowledge to make informed decisions and judgements in life.

THE “N” FRAMEWORK

As described in the previous sections, many researchers have put forward different models of knowledge a teacher should possess in order to teach effectively in the classroom. From the literature review, it became apparent to us that while a number of frameworks for teacher knowledge exist, none of these frameworks address numeracy knowledge, subject specific knowledge, and pedagogical content knowledge together. We argue that being an effective teacher of numeracy within any subject area requires all three components of knowledge and therefore have developed a new three-component model for teacher knowledge that we refer to as the “N” framework.

As discussed in the previous section, it is essential that teachers have a clear understanding of the term numeracy and what it means to teach numeracy within their subject area. If teachers are expected to incorporate numeracy into their teaching, then it is vital that teachers gain a deep understanding of the concept of numeracy along with their subject matter knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

We have discussed in detail the different models of teacher knowledge and therefore have decided that Shulman (1986) and Ball et al. (2008), along with Goos et al.'s (2014) numeracy model in the 21st century are the most comprehensive models to base the “N” Framework on. Teachers need to have a deep understanding of three main categories to teach students

effectively in any subject. The categories numeracy knowledge, subject specific knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge are presented in the “N” Framework in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The “N” Framework

The purpose of developing the “N” Framework is to establish a framework consisting of the three essential categories of knowledge required by teachers to teach numeracy in any subject across the curriculum effectively. We believe that the “N” framework can be used to guide teachers in their teaching of numeracy across the curriculum. It enables teachers to understand numeracy and how it can be embedded in the teaching of their subject.

Numeracy Knowledge Pillar

The first pillar of the “N” Framework is the numeracy knowledge block. This pillar represents the nature of numeracy in the 21st century. This pillar contains five different dimensions Contexts, Mathematical Knowledge, Dispositions, Tools and Critical Orientation. These components of numeracy knowledge, as discussed in the previous section are critical for a teacher in the teaching of numeracy within their subject area. If a teacher understands the concept of numeracy, they will be able to embed this in their teaching and this will further enhance the students’ development of numeracy skills for the future.

Subject Specific Knowledge Pillar:

The next pillar of the “N” Framework that we developed is the subject specific knowledge pillar. The authors looked at many different theories and frameworks for teacher knowledge, but the two that emerged the most suitably aligned to integrate with numeracy for us were Shulman’s Knowledge Growth in Teaching (1986) and more recently, Ball et al’s Content Knowledge for Teaching (2008). Both Shulman (1986) and Ball et al. (2008) highlight the importance of specific subject knowledge, with categories of common content knowledge and specialised content knowledge. We chose to exclude the knowledge at the mathematical horizon domain as this is specific to the teaching of mathematics and cannot be utilised in a general teacher knowledge framework. While we do not believe in a hierarchy of knowledge, we do believe that all teachers must possess a proficient level of subject-specific knowledge as well as numeracy knowledge.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge Bridge

Pedagogical content knowledge is the bridge and connection between the pillars of numeracy knowledge and subject specific knowledge within the proposed “N” framework. This is the connection between a numerate person and a person who specialises in a particular subject

area such as science, business studies or mathematics etc. Being able to take both categories of knowledge and convey this knowledge through their teaching is at the core of this framework and is known as pedagogical content knowledge. Pedagogical content knowledge is the bridge and link between a numerate teacher being able to find the numeracy learning opportunities within their subject and develop this knowledge as part of the specific subject which in turn enables their students in becoming numerate citizens for the 21st century. The three pillars complement each other in such a way that numeracy knowledge is linked through the bridge of pedagogical content knowledge and embedded in the subject specific knowledge which enables a teacher to develop the numeracy knowledge of his/her students in the different subject areas across the school curriculum.

CONCLUSION

The field of numeracy in Ireland is complex. It is characterised by policy, a lack of resources/curricular materials and the absence of a unified definition of numeracy for teachers. Likewise, teacher knowledge is multifaceted in nature and thus is difficult to define. However, if teachers are expected to embed numeracy in all aspects of their teaching, it is critical that a numeracy framework for teaching is developed to guide teachers in the most effective way on how best to implement numeracy teaching within the school curriculum. Teacher knowledge matters and in order for students to learn effectively. It is essential that the teachers have a good understanding of all types of knowledge. The “N” framework addresses the issues of numeracy knowledge and teacher knowledge combined and we believe that this framework will help pre- service and in-service teachers become aware of the different knowledge domains required for teaching numeracy in any subject across the curriculum in post-primary schools in Ireland.

REFERENCES

- Bennison, A. (2015). Supporting teachers to embed numeracy across the curriculum: a sociocultural approach. *ZDM - International Journal on Mathematics Education*, 47(4), pp.561–573.
- Ball, D. L., Thames, M. H., & Phelps, G. (2008). Content knowledge for teaching: What makes it special. *Journal of teacher education*, 59(5), 389-407.
- Cockcroft, W. (1982). *Mathematics counts*. London: HMSO.
- Department of Education and Skills. (DES). (2011). *Literacy and numeracy learning for life: The national strategy to improve literacy and numeracy among children and young people 2011-2020*. Dublin: Author.
- Fennema, E., & Franke, M. L. (1992). Teachers' knowledge and its impact. In D. A. Grouws (Ed.), *Handbook of research on mathematics teaching and learning: A project of the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics* (pp. 147-164). New York, NY: Macmillan.
- Frejd, P., & Geiger, V. (2017). Exploring the notion of mathematical literacy in curricula documents. In G. Stillman, G. Kaiser & W. Blum. (Eds.), *Mathematical modelling and applications: Crossing and researching boundaries in mathematics education* (pp. 255-264). Cham: Springer. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-62968-1_22

- Geiger, V., Goos, M., & Forgasz, H. (2015). A rich interpretation of numeracy for the 21st century: A survey of the state of the field. *ZDM*, 47(4), 531-548.
- Goos, M., Geiger, V., & Dole, S. (2013). Designing rich numeracy tasks. Task design in mathematics education. *Proceedings of ICMI Study*, 22(1), pp. 589–597
- Goos, M., Geiger, V., & Dole, S. (2014). Transforming professional practice in numeracy teaching. In Y. Li, E. Silver, & S. Li (Eds.), *Transforming mathematics instruction: multiple approaches and practices* (pp. 81–102). New York: Springer.
- Goos, M., Geiger, V., Dole, S., Forgasz, H., & Bennison, A. (2019). *Numeracy across the curriculum: Research-based strategies for enhancing teaching and learning*. Sydney: Allen and Unwin.
- Jablonka, E. (2015). The evolvement of numeracy and mathematical literacy curricula and the construction of hierarchies of numerate or mathematically literate subjects. *ZDM*, 47(4), 599-609.
- Leder, G., Forgasz, H., Kalkhoven, N., & Geiger, V. (2015). Pre-service teachers and numeracy in and beyond the classroom. In M. Marshman, V. Geiger, & A. Bennison (Eds.). *Mathematics education in the margins* (Proceedings of the 38th annual conference of the Mathematics Education Research Group of Australasia), pp. 349–356. Sunshine Coast: MERGA.
- Ministry of Education (1959). *15 to 18: A report of the Central Advisory Council for Education*. London: HMSO. Retrieved from <http://www.educationengland.org.uk/documents/crowther/crowther1959-1.html>
- Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological pedagogical content knowledge: A framework for teacher knowledge. *Teachers College Record*, 108(6), 1017-1054.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2016). *PISA 2015 assessment and analytical framework: Science, reading, mathematics and financial literacy*. Paris: Author.
- Rowland, T., & Turner, F. (2007). Developing and using the ‘Knowledge Quartet’: A framework for the observation of mathematics teaching. *The Mathematics Educator*, 10(1), 107-124.
- Shulman, L. S. (1986). Those who understand: Knowledge growth in teaching. *Educational Researcher*, 15(2), 4-14.
- Shulman, L. S. (1987). Knowledge and teaching: Foundations of the new reform. *Harvard Educational Review*, 57, 1-22.
- Van Driel, J. H., Verloop, N., & De Vos, W. (1998). Developing science teachers' pedagogical content knowledge. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 35(6), 673-695.
- Westwood, P. S. (2008). *What teachers need to know about numeracy*. Camberwell, Australia: Australian Council for Educational Research (ACER) Press.